

Three Algorithm Boxes

Algorithm 1: Hybrid Observer Mode Selection and Transition

Input: Estimated speed $\hat{\omega}_e$, thresholds $\omega_{low}=0.05\omega_{rated}$, $\omega_{high}=0.10\omega_{rated}$

Output: Observer mode (HFSWI / AEKF)

- 1: if $|\hat{\omega}_e| < \omega_{low}$ then
- 2: mode \leftarrow HFSWI
- 3: Inject V_{inj} at $\omega_{inj} = 2$ kHz
- 4: Demodulate PES via Equation (8)
- 5: Update θ via PLL
- 6: else if $|\hat{\omega}_e| > \omega_{high}$ then
- 7: if mode was HFSWI then
- 8: Initialize AEKF: $\hat{x}_0 \leftarrow \hat{x}_{HFSWI_final}$, $P_0 \leftarrow P_{transition}$
- 9: end if
- 10: mode \leftarrow AEKF
- 11: Execute Algorithm 2
- 12: else
- 13: mode \leftarrow previous_mode (hysteresis)
- 14: end if
- 15: return mode

Algorithm 2: AEKF Prediction and Update with Adaptive Covariance

Input: u_k (voltages), y_k (measured currents), $Q_{\{k-1\}}$, R

Output: \hat{x}_k (estimated states), Q_k (updated covariance)

- 1: // Prediction step
- 2: $\hat{x}_{\{k|k-1\}} \leftarrow f(\hat{x}_{\{k-1\}}, u_k)$
- 3: $P_{\{k|k-1\}} \leftarrow F_k P_{\{k-1\}} F_k^T + Q_{\{k-1\}}$

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4:
5: // Innovation
6:  $v_k \leftarrow y_k - H \hat{x}_{k|k-1}$ 
7:  $S_k \leftarrow H P_{k|k-1} H^T + R$ 
8:
9: // Adaptive covariance update (sliding window N=100)
10:  $C_{v,k} \leftarrow (1/N) \sum_{j=k-N+1}^k v_j v_j^T$ 
11:  $Q_k \leftarrow \alpha Q_{k-1} + (1-\alpha)(K_k C_{v,k} K_k^T)$  where  $\alpha=0.97$ 
12:
13: // Correction step
14:  $K_k \leftarrow P_{k|k-1} H^T S_k^{-1}$ 
15:  $\hat{x}_k \leftarrow \hat{x}_{k|k-1} + K_k v_k$ 
16:  $P_k \leftarrow (I - K_k H) P_{k|k-1}$ 
17: return  $\hat{x}_k, Q_k$ 

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Algorithm 3: OTA Update Procedure with Automatic Rollback

Input: Firmware image F_{new} , version v_{new} , signature sig , hash h_{ref}

Output: Updated active firmware or rollback to previous

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1: // Cloud initiates
2: cloud_publish("uav/ID/ota/trigger", {version, size, hash})
3:
4: // UAV downloads
5: for chunk in 0..N-1:
6:   download_chunk(chunk) via MQTT
7:   compute_incremental_hash(chunk)
8:   store_in_standby_partition(chunk)
9: end for
10: if final_hash  $\neq$  h_ref: reject_and_abort()

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11: if signature_verify(F_new, sig) = false: reject_and_abort()
12:
13: // Activation with watchdog
14: watchdog_set_timeout(60 seconds)
15: bootloader_activate(standby_partition)
16: system_reset()
17:
18: // New firmware runs
19: send_MQTT("health_ok")
20:
21: // Rollback condition (watchdog expiry or crash)
22: on watchdog_timeout or unhandled_exception:
23:   bootloader_revert_to(active_partition)
24:   system_reset()
25:   send_MQTT("rollback_completed", {reason})
26: end
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